

Prediction of Air Quality during 2010 Asian Games in Guangzhou

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Abstract—In this paper, a multiple attribute group decision making based on vague set model is developed for forecasting air quality during 2010 Asian Games in Guangzhou. The each air-quality monitoring station is considered as decision maker, the each date from 12th to 27th, November is considered as alternative. For attributes SO_2 , NO_2 and PM_{10} , the air quality in period of 16th Asian Games is done out according to in recent 3 years during November 12th to 27th, 2006, 2007 and 2008, respectively. The results showed that the air quality in period of Asian Games presents an ascending tendency.

keywords—Asian Games; air quality; Guangzhou; multiple attribute group decision making; vague set.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 16th Asian Games will be held during November 12th to 27th, 2010 in Guangzhou, China. This period will catch up with the annual comfortable season. At the same time, with the coming of Asian Games, air quality has been paid attention by more and more people. In this paper, we utilize the idea of multiple attribute decision making (MADM) by means of interval numbers and vague values, the air quality in period of 16th Asian Games was done out according to in recent 3 years during November 12th to 27th, 2006, 2007 and 2008, respectively.

The vague set, which is a generalization of the concept of a fuzzy set, has been introduced by Gau and Buehrer [1]. Up to date, we are alive to that decision method based on vague set is discussed under vague information environment. However, in the real-life world, the attribute value usually take the form of crisp number in order to statistical simpleness or convenience. How to transform crisp number into vague information and then obtain the order of alternatives in accordance with the order of vague values. It is interesting and important research topic[2-4]. In order to solve this problem, this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 we briefly describe vague sets and their order relation. Section 3 outlines the interval numbers and their operation, describes MADM and presents the idea that attribute values are transformed from real numbers into interval numbers, then from interval numbers into vague values, and develops an approach to MADM based on vague values. Section 4 provides a practical example to illustrate the developed approach. And finally, we conclude the paper in Section 5.

II. VAGUE SETS AND THEIR ORDER RELATION

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\}$ be a discourse, then a vague set [1] A in X having the form:

$$A = \{ \langle x_i, [t_A(x_i), 1 - f_A(x_i)] \rangle \mid x_i \in X \} \quad (1)$$

which is characterized by a truth-membership function t_A and a false-membership function f_A , where

$$t_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x_i \in X \rightarrow t_A(x_i) \in [0, 1],$$

$$f_A : X \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad x_i \in X \rightarrow f_A(x_i) \in [0, 1],$$

with the condition

$$t_A(x_i) + f_A(x_i) \leq 1, \quad \text{for all } x_i \in X$$

The grade of membership of x_i in A is bounded to a subinterval $[t_A(x_i), 1 - f_A(x_i)]$ of $[0, 1]$. Gau and Buehrer [1] called interval $[t_A(x_i), 1 - f_A(x_i)]$ a vague value.

Let $\tilde{\alpha} = [t_{\tilde{\alpha}}, 1 - f_{\tilde{\alpha}}]$ and $\tilde{\beta} = [t_{\tilde{\beta}}, 1 - f_{\tilde{\beta}}]$ be two vague values, then

- 1) $\tilde{\alpha} + \tilde{\beta} = [t_{\tilde{\alpha}} + t_{\tilde{\beta}} - t_{\tilde{\alpha}}t_{\tilde{\beta}}, 1 - f_{\tilde{\alpha}}f_{\tilde{\beta}}]$;
- 2) $\lambda\tilde{\alpha} = [1 - (1 - t_{\tilde{\alpha}})^\lambda, 1 - f_{\tilde{\alpha}}^\lambda], \lambda > 0$.

Definition 1. An weighted averaging operator [5] is a mapping WA: $\Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega$ such that

$$WA(\tilde{\alpha}_1, \tilde{\alpha}_2, \dots, \tilde{\alpha}_n) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \tilde{\alpha}_j \quad (2)$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is the weight vector of the vague values $\tilde{\alpha}_j (j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$, $w_j \geq 0$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$, Ω is the set of all vague values.

Assume that $\tilde{\alpha}_j = [t_{\tilde{\alpha}_j}, 1 - f_{\tilde{\alpha}_j}] (j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ are n vague value, $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is the weight vector of the vague values, there vague values weighted averaging shown as:

$$\left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - t_{\tilde{\alpha}_j})^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n f_{\tilde{\alpha}_j}^{w_j} \right] \quad (3)$$

Chen and Tan [6] introduced a score function s of a vague value, which is represented as follows.

Let $\tilde{\alpha} = [t_{\tilde{\alpha}}, 1 - f_{\tilde{\alpha}}]$ be a vague value, the score of $\tilde{\alpha}$ can be evaluated by the score function s shown as:

$$s(\tilde{\alpha}) = t_{\tilde{\alpha}} - f_{\tilde{\alpha}} \quad (4)$$

where $s(\tilde{\alpha}) \in [-1, 1]$. The score of $s(\tilde{\alpha})$ is directly related to the deviation between $t_{\tilde{\alpha}}$ and $f_{\tilde{\alpha}}$, i.e., the higher the score $s(\tilde{\alpha})$ and, thus, the larger the vague value $\tilde{\alpha}$.

Later, Hong and Choi [7] defined an accuracy function h

$$h(\tilde{\alpha}) = t_{\tilde{\alpha}} + f_{\tilde{\alpha}} \quad (5)$$

to evaluate the degree of accuracy of the degree of membership of the vague value $\tilde{\alpha}$, where $h(\tilde{\alpha}) \in [0, 1]$. The larger the value of $h(\tilde{\alpha})$, the higher the degree of accuracy of the vague value $\tilde{\alpha}$.

Based on the score function s and the accuracy function h , in the following, we give an order relation between any pair of vague values, which is defined as follows.

Definition 2. Let $\tilde{\alpha} = [t_{\tilde{\alpha}}, 1 - f_{\tilde{\alpha}}]$ and $\tilde{\beta} = [t_{\tilde{\beta}}, 1 - f_{\tilde{\beta}}]$ be two vague values, s and h be score function and accuracy function, respectively, then

- If $s(\tilde{\alpha}) < s(\tilde{\beta})$, then $\tilde{\alpha}$ is smaller than $\tilde{\beta}$, denoted by $\tilde{\alpha} < \tilde{\beta}$.
- If $s(\tilde{\alpha}) = s(\tilde{\beta})$, then
 - 1) If $h(\tilde{\alpha}) = h(\tilde{\beta})$, then $\tilde{\alpha}$ and $\tilde{\beta}$ represent the same information, denoted by $\tilde{\alpha} = \tilde{\beta}$.
 - 2) If $h(\tilde{\alpha}) < h(\tilde{\beta})$, then $\tilde{\alpha}$ is smaller than $\tilde{\beta}$, denoted by $\tilde{\alpha} < \tilde{\beta}$.

III. INTERVAL NUMBERS AND ALGORITHM BASED ON VAGUE VALUES

Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m\}$ be a discrete set of alternatives, $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ be a set of attributes, and $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ be the vector of attribute weights, where $w_j \geq 0$, $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$. Let $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_t\}$ be the set of decision makers, $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_t)^T$ be the weight vector of decision makers, where $\lambda_j \geq 0$, $\sum_{j=1}^t \lambda_j = 1$.

Let $X_k = (x_{ij}^k)_{mn}$ be decision matrix of k th ($k = 1, 2, \dots, t$) decision maker. Assume

$$x_{ij}^l = \min_{1 \leq k \leq t} x_{ij}^k, \quad x_{ij}^u = \max_{1 \leq k \leq t} x_{ij}^k \quad (6)$$

then we have decision matrix $X = ([x_{ij}^l, x_{ij}^u])_{mn}$.

Definition 3. Let $a = [a^l, a^u] = \{x | 0 \leq a^l \leq x \leq a^u\}$, then a is called a nonnegative interval number. Especially, a is a nonnegative real number if $a^l = a^u$.

In general, there are benefit attributes (larger-the-better) and cost attributes (smaller-the-better) in MADM problems, and the dimension of different attributes may be different. In order to measure all attributes in dimensionless units, we can normalize each attribute value $[x_{ij}^l, x_{ij}^u]$ in X into a corresponding element $[r_{ij}^l, r_{ij}^u]$ using the following formulas [8]:

$$\begin{cases} r_{ij}^l = \frac{x_{ij}^l}{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij}^u} \\ r_{ij}^u = \frac{x_{ij}^u}{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij}^l} \end{cases}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (7)$$

for the benefit attribute (larger-the-better).

$$\begin{cases} r_{ij}^l = \frac{1/x_{ij}^u}{\sum_{j=1}^n (1/x_{ij}^l)} \\ r_{ij}^u = \frac{1/x_{ij}^l}{\sum_{j=1}^n (1/x_{ij}^u)} \end{cases}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (8)$$

for the cost attribute (smaller-the-better).

Thus, the normalized decision matrix $R = ([r_{ij}^l, r_{ij}^u])_{mn}$ is obtained. We regard attribute value $[x_{ij}^l, x_{ij}^u]$ in R as vague value. For any given vector of attribute weights $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$, we aggregate all vague values in each line of R using Eq. (2), and obtain overall evaluating value of each alternative as following:

$$[x_1^l, x_1^u], [x_2^l, x_2^u], \dots, [x_m^l, x_m^u] \quad (9)$$

In the following, we apply the above statement to MADM based on vague information. The method involves the following steps:

Step 1. Let $X_k = (x_{ij}^k)_{mn}$ be decision matrix of k th ($k = 1, 2, \dots, t$) decision maker. we aggregate the group decision values $\{x_{kj}^i\}_{k=1}^t$ into interval number $[x_{ij}^l, x_{ij}^u]$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) by using Eq. (6), then decision matrix $X = ([x_{ij}^l, x_{ij}^u])_{mn}$ is obtained.

Step 2. Utilize the Eq. (7) or Eq.(8) to normalize the X into $R = ([r_{ij}^l, r_{ij}^u])_{mn}$.

Step 3. Aggregate all normalized evaluating values of alternative with respect to attributes in each line of R using Eq. (2), and overall evaluating values of alternatives Eq.(9) are obtained.

Step 4. Calculate the scores and the accuracy degrees of vague values in Eq. (9) by using Eq. (4) and (5), respectively, and utilize the scores and the accuracy degrees to rank them by Definition 2.

Step 5. Rank all the alternatives x_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$) and select the best one in accordance with the order of vague values in Eq. (9).

IV. ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE

Guangzhou is located in the south of China-mainland, central south of Guangdong Province. It is close to South China Sea and center is located latitude $23^{\circ}06'32''$ N and longitude $114^{\circ}15'53''$ E (see fig.1). The climatic environment of Guangzhou is belongs to subtropical. Its annual average temperature is 22.8°C , with the minimum temperature about 0°C and the maximum temperature 38°C . There are comfortable climate. The difference of annual average temperature is one of minimum in big city of China. Guangzhou has always enjoyed the reputation of the Flower City.

In following, we give comprehensive evaluation of air quality in recent 3 years during November 12^{th} to 27^{th} , 2006, 2007 and 2008, respectively. And forecast the air quality in Guangzhou City during 2010 Asian Games basis for the results of comprehensive evaluation. In this evaluation, the each air-quality monitoring station can be considered as decision maker, i.e., $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_9\} = \{\text{Xichun, Baogang, Jixiang Road, Gymnasium East, Luhu, Chisha, Huangpu Dasha, Fanyu City Bridge, Xinhua Station in Huadu District}\}$. The each date

Fig. 1. Geographic locations of air-quality monitoring stations (shown in dots) in Guangzhou City

from November 12th to 27th can be considered as alternative, and assume that, $\{x_{12}, x_{13}, \dots, x_{27}\}$, $\{y_{12}, y_{13}, \dots, y_{27}\}$ and $\{z_{12}, z_{13}, \dots, z_{27}\}$ are sets of alternatives from 12th to 27th, November, 2006, 2007 and 2008, respectively. $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3\} = \{SO_2, NO_2, PM_{10}\}$ is the set of attributes.

First, by Step 1, we can transform all collected data [9] from November 12th to 27th, 2006, 2007 and 2008, respectively, into Table 1-3, correspondingly.

By Step 2, we can normalize the Table 1-3 into Table 4-6, respectively.

The weight of attributes is determined according to the Implementing Details for Urban Environmental Comprehensive Treatment and Quantitative Examination during the 11th Five-Year Plan (The General Office of General Administration of Environmental Protection [2006], No. 36)[10], which is promulgated by General Administration of Environmental Protection of the People's Republic of China. The weights of PM_{10} , SO_2 , and NO_2 are 0.4, 0.4 and 0.2, respectively.

By Step 3, Aggregate all normalized evaluating values in each line of Table 4-6, respectively. we have overall normalized evaluating values of each day from November 12th to 27th, as the form of vague value following:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x}_{12} &= [0.0282, 0.1604], \tilde{x}_{13} = [0.0160, 0.0809], \\ \tilde{x}_{14} &= [0.0165, 0.0810], \tilde{x}_{15} = [0.0235, 0.1427], \\ \tilde{x}_{16} &= [0.0176, 0.0651], \tilde{x}_{17} = [0.0172, 0.0709], \\ \tilde{x}_{18} &= [0.0195, 0.0861], \tilde{x}_{19} = [0.0324, 0.1397], \\ \tilde{x}_{20} &= [0.0495, 0.3196], \tilde{x}_{21} = [0.0306, 0.1442], \\ \tilde{x}_{22} &= [0.0398, 0.2249], \tilde{x}_{23} = [0.0293, 0.1543], \\ \tilde{x}_{24} &= [0.0403, 0.2475], \tilde{x}_{25} = [0.0204, 0.0983], \\ \tilde{x}_{26} &= [0.0175, 0.0766], \tilde{x}_{27} = [0.0400, 0.2523]. \end{aligned}$$

Compute the scores of $\tilde{x}_i$ ($i = 12, 13, \dots, 27$) by Step 4, we have

$$s(\tilde{x}_{12}) = -0.8114, s(\tilde{x}_{13}) = -0.9031, s(\tilde{x}_{14}) = -0.9025,$$

TABLE I
AIR QUALITY DURING NOVEMBER 12th TO 27th, 2006 IN GUANGZHOU

Date	SO_2	NO_2	PM_{10}
12	[19,40]	[13,53]	[51,89]
13	[46,83]	[30,92]	[64,137]
14	[57,85]	[24,107]	[67,119]
15	[18,56]	[17,62]	[63,94]
16	[50,79]	[46,89]	[77,117]
17	[46,80]	[34,93]	[84,120]
18	[34,80]	[44,88]	[57,95]
19	[18,49]	[27,45]	[43,60]
20	[9,23]	[16,35]	[14,47]
21	[23,53]	[21,43]	[34,66]
22	[13,33]	[21,39]	[20,54]
23	[16,55]	[27,54]	[38,64]
24	[8,27]	[21,42]	[38,61]
25	[30,92]	[32,78]	[55,85]
26	[37,96]	[46,107]	[69,99]
27	[9,30]	[25,42]	[23,56]

TABLE II
AIR QUALITY DURING NOVEMBER 12th TO 27th, 2007 IN GUANGZHOU

Date	SO_2	NO_2	PM_{10}
12	[40,88]	[40,126]	[75,106]
13	[60,90]	[64,117]	[71,100]
14	[66,106]	[84,134]	[80,114]
15	[56,100]	[92,141]	[82,123]
16	[66,104]	[89,160]	[84,150]
17	[71,108]	[95,157]	[79,136]
18	[37,63]	[27,106]	[78,129]
19	[22,44]	[17,50]	[22,61]
20	[21,36]	[17,49]	[18,57]
21	[26,34]	[18,70]	[34,65]
22	[28,39]	[20,84]	[44,75]
23	[22,46]	[20,98]	[44,78]
24	[23,43]	[21,100]	[45,81]
25	[24,41]	[22,103]	[53,84]
26	[21,45]	[25,78]	[46,88]
27	[35,55]	[16,45]	[54,92]

$$\begin{aligned} s(\tilde{x}_{15}) &= -0.8338, s(\tilde{x}_{16}) = -0.9173, s(\tilde{x}_{17}) = -0.9119, \\ s(\tilde{x}_{18}) &= -0.8944, s(\tilde{x}_{19}) = -0.8279, s(\tilde{x}_{20}) = -0.6309, \\ s(\tilde{x}_{21}) &= -0.8252, s(\tilde{x}_{22}) = -0.7353, s(\tilde{x}_{23}) = -0.8164, \\ s(\tilde{x}_{24}) &= -0.7122, s(\tilde{x}_{25}) = -0.9030, s(\tilde{x}_{26}) = -0.9059, \\ s(\tilde{x}_{27}) &= -0.7077. \end{aligned}$$

By Step 4, the order relation of vague values $\tilde{x}_i$ ($i = 12, 13, \dots, 27$) is follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{x}_{20} &\geq \tilde{x}_{27} \geq \tilde{x}_{24} \geq \tilde{x}_{22} \geq \tilde{x}_{12} \geq \tilde{x}_{23} \geq \tilde{x}_{21} \geq \tilde{x}_{19} \\ &\geq \tilde{x}_{15} \geq \tilde{x}_{18} \geq \tilde{x}_{14} \geq \tilde{x}_{25} \geq \tilde{x}_{13} \geq \tilde{x}_{26} \geq \tilde{x}_{17} \geq \tilde{x}_{16} \end{aligned}$$

The comprehensive order relation of air quality during November 12th to 27th, 2006 in Guangzhou as following:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{20} &\succ x_{27} \succ x_{24} \succ x_{22} \succ x_{12} \succ x_{23} \succ x_{21} \succ x_{19} \\ &\succ x_{15} \succ x_{18} \succ x_{14} \succ x_{25} \succ x_{13} \succ x_{26} \succ x_{17} \succ x_{16} \end{aligned}$$

TABLE III
AIR QUALITY DURING NOVEMBER 12th TO 27th, 2008 IN GUANGZHOU

Date	SO ₂	NO ₂	PM ₁₀
12	[10,33]	[12,49]	[28,61]
13	[9,53]	[25,79]	[46,73]
14	[10,53]	[28,73]	[36,75]
15	[12,86]	[30,80]	[45,91]
16	[15,78]	[32,97]	[51,100]
17	[13,70]	[24,97]	[52,92]
18	[12,61]	[16,44]	[54,84]
19	[11,25]	[12,32]	[32,60]
20	[11,30]	[18,37]	[22,55]
21	[9,59]	[17,59]	[15,66]
22	[13,99]	[29,98]	[53,94]
23	[23,102]	[34,99]	[59,113]
24	[25,62]	[25,57]	[59,97]
25	[15,43]	[15,46]	[33,65]
26	[20,40]	[16,59]	[38,72]
27	[18,49]	[19,67]	[43,82]

Similar to deal with Table 5, we have the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y}_{12} &= [0.0226, 0.0972], \tilde{y}_{13} = [0.0232, 0.0711], \\ \tilde{y}_{14} &= [0.0201, 0.0615], \tilde{y}_{15} = [0.0197, 0.0633], \\ \tilde{y}_{16} &= [0.0174, 0.0594], \tilde{y}_{17} = [0.0180, 0.0589], \\ \tilde{y}_{18} &= [0.0247, 0.1070], \tilde{y}_{19} = [0.0437, 0.2295], \\ \tilde{y}_{20} &= [0.0492, 0.2558], \tilde{y}_{21} = [0.0460, 0.1808], \\ \tilde{y}_{22} &= [0.0398, 0.1558], \tilde{y}_{23} = [0.0355, 0.1687], \\ \tilde{y}_{24} &= [0.0361, 0.1621], \tilde{y}_{25} = [0.0364, 0.1499], \\ \tilde{y}_{26} &= [0.0351, 0.1576], \tilde{y}_{27} = [0.0345, 0.1540]. \end{aligned}$$

The scores of $\tilde{y}_i (i = 12, 13, \dots, 27)$ as following:

$$\begin{aligned} s(\tilde{y}_{12}) &= -0.8862, s(\tilde{y}_{13}) = -0.9057, s(\tilde{y}_{14}) = -0.9184, \\ s(\tilde{y}_{15}) &= -0.9170, s(\tilde{y}_{16}) = -0.9232, s(\tilde{y}_{17}) = -0.9231, \\ s(\tilde{y}_{18}) &= -0.8683, s(\tilde{y}_{19}) = -0.7268, s(\tilde{y}_{20}) = -0.6950, \\ s(\tilde{y}_{21}) &= -0.7732, s(\tilde{y}_{22}) = -0.8044, s(\tilde{y}_{23}) = -0.7958, \\ s(\tilde{y}_{24}) &= -0.8018, s(\tilde{y}_{25}) = -0.8137, s(\tilde{y}_{26}) = -0.8073, \\ s(\tilde{y}_{27}) &= -0.8115. \end{aligned}$$

By Step 4, the order relation of vague values $\tilde{y}_i (i = 12, 13, \dots, 27)$ is follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{y}_{20} \succ \tilde{y}_{19} \succ \tilde{y}_{21} \succ \tilde{y}_{23} \succ \tilde{y}_{24} \succ \tilde{y}_{26} \succ \tilde{y}_{22} \succ \tilde{y}_{27} \\ \succ \tilde{y}_{25} \succ \tilde{y}_{18} \succ \tilde{y}_{12} \succ \tilde{y}_{13} \succ \tilde{y}_{15} \succ \tilde{y}_{14} \succ \tilde{y}_{17} \succ \tilde{y}_{16} \end{aligned}$$

The comprehensive order relation of air quality during November 12th to 27th, 2007 in Guangzhou as following:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{20} \succ y_{19} \succ y_{21} \succ y_{23} \succ y_{24} \succ y_{26} \succ y_{22} \succ y_{27} \\ \succ y_{25} \succ y_{18} \succ y_{12} \succ y_{13} \succ y_{15} \succ y_{14} \succ y_{17} \succ y_{16} \end{aligned}$$

TABLE IV
THE NORMALIZED AIR QUALITY DURING NOVEMBER 12th TO 27th, 2006 IN GUANGZHOU

Date	SO ₂	NO ₂	PM ₁₀
12	[0.0289,0.1608]	[0.0287,0.2781]	[0.0273,0.0941]
13	[0.0139,0.0664]	[0.0165,0.1205]	[0.0177,0.0750]
14	[0.0136,0.0536]	[0.0142,0.1507]	[0.0204,0.0716]
15	[0.0207,0.1698]	[0.0245,0.2127]	[0.0259,0.0762]
16	[0.0146,0.0611]	[0.0171,0.0786]	[0.0208,0.0623]
17	[0.0145,0.0664]	[0.0164,0.1063]	[0.0203,0.0571]
18	[0.0145,0.0899]	[0.0173,0.0822]	[0.0256,0.0842]
19	[0.0236,0.1698]	[0.0338,0.1339]	[0.0405,0.1116]
20	[0.0503,0.3396]	[0.0435,0.2260]	[0.0517,0.3426]
21	[0.0218,0.1329]	[0.0354,0.1722]	[0.0368,0.1412]
22	[0.0350,0.2351]	[0.0390,0.1722]	[0.0450,0.2400]
23	[0.0210,0.1910]	[0.0282,0.1339]	[0.0380,0.1263]
24	[0.0428,0.3820]	[0.0362,0.1722]	[0.0399,0.1263]
25	[0.0126,0.1019]	[0.0195,0.1130]	[0.0286,0.0873]
26	[0.0120,0.0826]	[0.0142,0.0786]	[0.0246,0.0696]
27	[0.0386,0.3396]	[0.0362,0.1446]	[0.0434,0.2087]

TABLE V
THE NORMALIZED AIR QUALITY DURING NOVEMBER 12th TO 27th, 2007 IN GUANGZHOU

Date	SO ₂	NO ₂	PM ₁₀
12	[0.0225,0.0856]	[0.0134,0.1354]	[0.0272,0.0740]
13	[0.0220,0.0571]	[0.0145,0.0846]	[0.0288,0.0782]
14	[0.0187,0.0519]	[0.0126,0.0645]	[0.0253,0.0694]
15	[0.0198,0.0612]	[0.0120,0.0589]	[0.0234,0.0677]
16	[0.0190,0.0519]	[0.0106,0.0609]	[0.0192,0.0661]
17	[0.0183,0.0482]	[0.0108,0.0570]	[0.0212,0.0703]
18	[0.0314,0.0926]	[0.0160,0.2006]	[0.0224,0.0712]
19	[0.0450,0.1557]	[0.0338,0.3186]	[0.0473,0.2524]
20	[0.0550,0.1631]	[0.0345,0.3186]	[0.0506,0.3085]
21	[0.0582,0.1317]	[0.0242,0.3009]	[0.0444,0.1633]
22	[0.0508,0.1223]	[0.0201,0.2708]	[0.0385,0.1262]
23	[0.0430,0.1557]	[0.0173,0.2708]	[0.0370,0.1262]
24	[0.0461,0.1489]	[0.0169,0.2579]	[0.0356,0.1234]
25	[0.0483,0.1427]	[0.0164,0.2462]	[0.0343,0.1048]
26	[0.0440,0.1631]	[0.0217,0.2166]	[0.0328,0.1207]
27	[0.0360,0.0978]	[0.0376,0.3385]	[0.0313,0.1028]

Similar to deal with Table 6, we have the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{z}_{12} &= [0.0296, 0.2583], \tilde{z}_{13} = [0.0216, 0.0711], \\ \tilde{z}_{14} &= [0.0216, 0.2103], \tilde{z}_{15} = [0.0168, 0.1752], \\ \tilde{z}_{16} &= [0.0157, 0.1460], \tilde{z}_{17} = [0.0180, 0.1668], \\ \tilde{z}_{18} &= [0.0217, 0.1899], \tilde{z}_{19} = [0.0357, 0.2384], \\ \tilde{z}_{20} &= [0.0339, 0.2430], \tilde{z}_{21} = [0.0234, 0.3124], \\ \tilde{z}_{22} &= [0.0154, 0.1611], \tilde{z}_{23} = [0.0137, 0.1091], \\ \tilde{z}_{24} &= [0.0189, 0.1125], \tilde{z}_{25} = [0.0268, 0.1917], \\ \tilde{z}_{26} &= [0.0248, 0.1600], \tilde{z}_{27} = [0.0213, 0.1537]. \end{aligned}$$

The scores of $\tilde{z}_i (i = 12, 13, \dots, 27)$ as following:

$$\begin{aligned} s(\tilde{z}_{12}) &= -0.7121, s(\tilde{z}_{13}) = -0.7591, s(\tilde{z}_{14}) = -0.7681, \\ s(\tilde{z}_{15}) &= -0.8080, s(\tilde{z}_{16}) = -0.8383, s(\tilde{z}_{17}) = -0.8152, \end{aligned}$$

TABLE VI
THE NORMALIZED AIR QUALITY DURING NOVEMBER 12th TO 27th, 2008
IN GUANGZHOU

Date	SO ₂	NO ₂	PM ₁₀
12	[0.0243,0.3143]	[0.0252,0.3049]	[0.0372,0.1713]
13	[0.0151,0.3492]	[0.0156,0.1464]	[0.0311,0.1043]
14	[0.0151,0.3143]	[0.0169,0.1307]	[0.0302,0.1333]
15	[0.0093,0.2619]	[0.0154,0.1220]	[0.0249,0.1066]
16	[0.0103,0.2095]	[0.0127,0.1144]	[0.0227,0.0941]
17	[0.0115,0.2418]	[0.0176,0.1525]	[0.0247,0.0923]
18	[0.0131,0.2619]	[0.0280,0.2287]	[0.0270,0.0888]
19	[0.0321,0.2857]	[0.0385,0.3049]	[0.0378,0.1499]
20	[0.0267,0.2857]	[0.0333,0.2033]	[0.0412,0.2181]
21	[0.0136,0.3492]	[0.0209,0.2153]	[0.0344,0.3198]
22	[0.0081,0.2418]	[0.0126,0.1262]	[0.0241,0.0905]
23	[0.0079,0.1367]	[0.0125,0.1076]	[0.0201,0.0813]
24	[0.0129,0.1257]	[0.0216,0.1464]	[0.0234,0.0813]
25	[0.0187,0.2095]	[0.0268,0.2440]	[0.0349,0.1454]
26	[0.0200,0.1572]	[0.0209,0.2287]	[0.0315,0.1262]
27	[0.0164,0.1746]	[0.0184,0.1926]	[0.0277,0.1116]

$$\begin{aligned}
s(\tilde{z}_{18}) &= -0.7884, s(\tilde{z}_{19}) = -0.7259, s(\tilde{z}_{20}) = -0.7231, \\
s(\tilde{z}_{21}) &= -0.6642, s(\tilde{z}_{22}) = -0.8235, s(\tilde{z}_{23}) = -0.8772, \\
s(\tilde{z}_{24}) &= -0.8686, s(\tilde{z}_{25}) = -0.7815, s(\tilde{z}_{26}) = -0.8152, \\
s(\tilde{z}_{27}) &= -0.8250.
\end{aligned}$$

Which $s(\tilde{z}_{17})$ and $s(\tilde{z}_{26})$ are equal, we further use accuracy function h , since

$$h(\tilde{z}_{17}) = 0.8512, h(\tilde{z}_{26}) = 0.8648.$$

by Definition 2, have

$$h(\tilde{z}_{17}) < h(\tilde{z}_{26}).$$

By Step 4, the order relation of vague values $\tilde{z}_i (i = 12, 13, \dots, 27)$ is follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{z}_{21} &\geq \tilde{z}_{12} \geq \tilde{z}_{20} \geq \tilde{z}_{19} \geq \tilde{z}_{13} \geq \tilde{z}_{14} \geq \tilde{z}_{25} \geq \tilde{z}_{18} \\
&\geq \tilde{z}_{15} \geq \tilde{z}_{26} \geq \tilde{z}_{17} \geq \tilde{z}_{22} \geq \tilde{z}_{27} \geq \tilde{z}_{16} \geq \tilde{z}_{24} \geq \tilde{z}_{23}
\end{aligned}$$

The comprehensive order relation of air quality during November 12th to 27th, 2008 in Guangzhou as following:

$$\begin{aligned}
z_{21} &\succ z_{12} \succ z_{20} \succ z_{19} \succ z_{13} \succ z_{14} \succ z_{25} \succ z_{18} \\
&\succ z_{15} \succ z_{26} \succ z_{17} \succ z_{22} \succ z_{27} \succ z_{16} \succ z_{24} \succ z_{23}
\end{aligned}$$

The results of comprehensive evaluation of air quality in Guangzhou during November 12th to 27th, 2006, 2007, 2008 and mean value, respectively is showed in figure 2.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we utilize the idea of MADM by means of interval numbers and vague values, establish a model to evaluate air quality. By the model, the air quality was comprehensive evaluated in recent 3 years during November 12th to 27th, 2006, 2007 and 2008, respectively. The air quality in period of 16nd Asian Games was done out according to the results.

Fig. 2. Comprehensive evaluation of air quality in Guangzhou during November 12th to 27th, 2006, 2007, 2008 and mean value, respectively

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